

SUPERPLASTIC FORMING OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE SHEETS REINFORCED BY SiC PARTICLES

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SUMMARY: Superplastic forming of aluminum alloy matrix composites reinforced by SiC particles was studied from their basic deformation properties in a tensile test to the forming applications of various shape parts by gas pressure. The tensile test was performed at elevated temperatures to characterize the optimum strain rate for superplasticity. It is much higher for the aluminum matrix composite sheets than that of a conventional 7475 alloy sheet. One of the forming tests is an axisymmetric conical part, in which the composite sheet is biaxially formed at high strain rate around the suitable rate characterized in the tensile test. It can be successfully formed even in biaxial forming at high strain rate. The others are box shape parts with different geometry, in which the sheet is formed at lower strain rate than that in the conical part forming. The composite sheet can be also successfully formed into box part as well as the conventional 7475 alloy sheet.

KEYWORDS: Metal matrix composite, Superplastic forming, Aluminum alloy, SiC particle, High strain rate, Tensile test, Forming test

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) exhibit a unique combination of high modulus and strength at room temperature and have possibility for secondary forming that is difficult for fiber reinforced composites. The development of forming process is very important to apply the discontinuously reinforced MMC for complex shape products, because the MMC has some difficulties in the conventional manufacturing process including cold forming and machining due to its excellent strength and wear resistance.

Recently superplastic behavior of the discontinuously reinforced aluminum matrix composite was reported in some works[1-3]. Therefore the superplastic forming is one of the useful secondary processes, and it enables precise dimension forming by low applied load. Especially, it is very useful for the MMC because its superplastic behavior appears at higher strain rate than that of conventional aluminum alloys. It means that the forming process enables also high productivity.

In the present work, superplastic deformation behavior in a tensile test and forming applications of various shape parts were investigated for aluminum alloy matrix composites reinforced by SiC particles. The tensile test was performed at elevated temperature to

characterize the optimum strain rate for the superplasticity. One of the forming tests is an axisymmetric conical part, which is selected to examine the possibility of the high strain rate superplasticity in biaxial forming. The others are box shape parts, which are selected as basic shapes aiming the real complex shape parts design.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Several aluminum matrix composites reinforced by SiC particles were prepared for the experiment. They are SiCp/2124 and SiCp/8090, and their volume fractions of SiC_p are 17% in both materials. They were both commercially fabricated by P/M method and received as annealed sheets with a nominal thickness of 2mm. Then they were hot rolled into 1.0-1.5mm at 773K to control an initial thickness of the sheet. Conventional superplastic aluminum alloy 7475 was also prepared for comparison of the formability.

Tensile tests at elevated temperatures were performed under various cross-head speeds, and deformation characteristics were evaluated.

An axisymmetrical forming test of a conical part was performed by using the forming equipment shown in Fig.1 with compressed air up to 1 MPa, which enabled to form at high strain rate. The blank disk with 35mm diameter and 1mm thickness is set between a die and a holder, and they are heated in the furnace. The compressed air is inlet from the bottom after reaching the appropriate temperature, and the disk is formed into the conical shape along the die.

Other forming tests of box shape parts with different geometry were performed by using the die set shown in Fig.2 with Ar gas up to 3 MPa. A rectangular blank sheet with 1.5mm thickness is set between the preheated upper and lower dies, and the Ar gas is inlet from the center of the upper die. In this box shape forming, the gas pressure is not constant during the forming process, but it is controlled to the appropriate level which is theoretically predicted on the basis of simple assumptions. The forming tests were carried out in the conditions listed in Table 1. The distributions of the thickness strain of the formed parts were measured and compared among three materials sheets.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relationships between the total elongation and the strain rate of 7475 sheets and hot rolled composite sheets are compared in Fig.3. The larger superplastic elongation above 200% can be found in the composite sheets as well as the 7475 alloy. And the maximum elongation of the composites are observed at about 100 times higher strain rate than that in the conventional superplastic aluminum alloy 7475.

Fig.4 shows the appearances of the formed conical parts. They were completely formed in only a few seconds and it means the forming was performed at the rate of around 1×10^{-1} (/sec) which is the suitable rate obtained by the tensile test. From this result, it is confirmed that the superplasticity of the composites at high strain rate which is observed in the uniaxial tensile test is also recognized in the biaxial forming of a conical shape part. The surface of the formed part is smooth in general, but slightly rough surface and a small crack are observed only at the top of the cone. The thickness of the formed part decreases gradually from the flange to the top and the crack is occurred at the top, because the sheet is touched to a die face and its deformation is restricted gradually from the region near the flange during the forming.

The forming tests of box shape parts were performed at the strain rate between 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} /sec that is lower than the suitable rate for the superplasticity of the composites, because of the limit of the gas supply ability of the forming equipment which was fabricated for the conventional superplastic forming (strain rate: 1×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-4} /sec). The results of the forming tests are summarized in Table 1. In the table, “O” and “X” show that the box part was formed with success and unsuccess respectively. All materials were successfully formed in the boxes of type I and II, but a burst of the sheet was occurred in the forming of the type III box at the site shown by an arrow in the figure.

Appearances and sizes of the formed parts are shown in Fig.5. The surfaces of the formed parts were smooth similarly to the conical parts. As above mentioned, the forming rate is very low for the composites, while it is near the suitable one of the 7475 alloy. The m-values of the composites and 7475 sheets at the forming rate are 0.2 and 0.55 respectively. But the composites have the similar formability as the conventional superplastic aluminum even at low strain rate.

Fig.6 shows the longitudinal sections of the formed type II boxes. It can be found that the thickness is also decreased gradually from the flange to the corner along the side wall in all materials. The distributions of thickness reduction of the type II boxes are shown in Fig.7, which are measured from the center of a bottom to the flange along the line shown in the figure. The thickness reductions at the corners of the composite boxes are larger than that of the 7475 alloy.

During the forming process of the type II box, at first the blank sheet is freely bulged in the die, and then touched on the dieface at the side wall and the bottom wall. Finally the box corner is formed and the forming is finished. The forming gas pressure is about 5 to 10 times higher in the forming of the composites than that of the 7475 alloy. The difference of the gas pressure level will lead to the difference of the friction between the die and the sheet. Namely the friction in the case of the composites box is much larger than the 7475 alloy. Therefore, in the box of the composites, the sheet is locally formed in the corner because the sheet slide is restricted in the touched region due to the large friction. Then the thickness at the corner is much more decreased than the 7475 alloy. However the localization of deformation is better for the composite, because the local strain rate around the corner becomes very high and it enables the large elongation without a crack occurrence.

From such a reason, the box shape parts were formed successfully even at lower forming rate than that of the suitable strain rate for the superplasticity of the composite sheets. Therefore, deeper and more complex shape parts can be expected to be formed by the increase of the forming rate.

CONCLUSIONS

Superplastic behaviors of aluminum matrix composite sheets were investigated by the tensile test and the forming tests of conical and box shape parts.

The high strain rate superplasticity of the composite sheets was observed in the tensile tests. And axisymmetric conical part was successfully formed at such a high strain rate. Box shape parts were also successfully formed even at lower forming rate, because the local strain rate around the corner becomes very high and it enables the large elongation without a crack occurrence.

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Fig.1 Schematic view of the forming equipment for conical part

Fig.2 Schematic view of the forming die set for box part

Fig.3 Relationship between elongation and strain rate of 7475 and hot rolled composite sheets

Material	SiC _p /2124 (1.1mm ³)	SiC _p /8090 (1.0mm ³)
Appearance		
Conditions	Temp : 798K Gas Pressure : up to 0.4MPa	Temp : 823K Gas Pressure : up to 0.8MPa

Fig.4 Appearance of the superplastically formed small cone at high strain rate

Table 1. Forming Condition and the Result of Box shape Forming Test

Material	Forming condition		Result of the forming test			type I
	Forming rate	Temp.	type I	type II	type III	
SiC _p /2124	5x10 ⁻³ (/sec)	773 (K)	○	○	×	type II
SiC _p /8090		833 (K)	○	○	×	
7475	5x10 ⁻⁴ (/sec)	773 (K)	○	○	×	type III

(1) box size (unit : mm)

(2) appearance

Fig.5 Appearance and size of superplastically formed box parts

Fig.6 Longitudinal sections of the type II boxes

Fig.7 Thickness strain of formed type II boxes